

Gruesome moment to cope with in life.

It is a disastrous consequence to serve two Masters: the external master and the eternal master. When I give my service to the fleshly master, I feel empty, hopeless, unfulfilled, etc. On the other hand, when I render my services to the eternal or Spiritual master, I feel relieved, ecstatic, enthusiastic, fulfilled, etc.

It would be naive; if I pursue my services with a master that makes me obsolete and useless to myself, friends, and my vision for life. I do not want to keep wearing a Mack all the time with the pretext to get admiration from external factors which I had found no strength and meaningless to my existence.

I am slowly demising from the inside, but I have the free will to choose to reject the external master and gain back my liberty. I can not just preach and teach when all I can see is poor leadership. It makes me sedated. It thrust me to the obligation of being a great leader in my niche. And to serve others with examples and not with void words from my so-called intelligent mind and heart, and to do something of significance.

Unfortunately, my earthly desire and lewd are trying to thwart me from embarking on this eternal transformation for the betterment and enhancement of my life and that of others, etc. Therefore, I must remain resilient and faithful to accomplish my purpose for posterity, integrity, legacy, and as an ambassador on earth of the Lord, Jesus Christ.

Lies are detrimental to our character, personality, and relationship with the creator.

We either stand up for righteousness, or we don't. We either stand up for the standard principles of God for his creation, or we can remain subject to sin as a slave. One of the things we take very common is lying tongue; that will never make us a genuine likeness of God on earth. *When he lies, the devil. He speaks out of his character, for he is a liar and the father of lies.*

How we appear to others is useless, but personality and character are the most important attributes we can boast of in God, the creator. To be a leader, we have to learn to lead with examples and not words or void words alone. I never understood this conception until I have found in myself the leader and potential. The process is about living a life that signifies truth, a good model that leads with example.

We must try to *walk our talk* if we want to transition from being a boy to a real man. A real man is a person who knows who he is and living in that personality not because he is under an obligation but steady he knows that it is the true nature of being born of the likeness and image of a righteous God. True leaders lead with an example, live for legacy and integrity. They are readers, critical-thinkers, problems solver, etc. Accountable and not avoidance. They take responsibility for their actions, whether negative or positive. They are always the last to be celebrated and accredited.

I am aware that everybody will not agree with my perspective in part or perhaps as a whole. My sincere desire is not to impose on others my conclusion but to stimulate a conversion that eventually leads to better development practices in discipline contexts. My hope and prayers as I share my thoughts with you that I have learned through my experiences, and now I will provide insights and perhaps be a blessing to you.

I Pray, the Lord, help us to know the truth and be liberated from knowledge of lies to maintain the trust of our loved ones and others.